

Watershed Development Policies and Their Impact on Farmers in the Marathwada Region

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Abstract:

Watershed development has emerged as a critical policy intervention for sustainable agricultural and rural development in semi-arid regions of India. The Marathwada region of Maharashtra, characterized by erratic rainfall, recurrent droughts, groundwater depletion, and agrarian distress, has been a major focus area for watershed development programmes. The present study examines the impact of watershed development policies on farmers in the Marathwada region, with special reference to changes in landholding patterns, irrigation status, income sources, livelihood security, environmental sustainability, and farmers' perceptions. The study is based on primary data collected from 150 farmers using a structured interview schedule during 2021–22. Comparative analysis of pre- and post-watershed conditions reveals significant improvements in irrigation coverage, groundwater recharge, crop productivity, income diversification, drinking water availability, and environmental quality. The findings suggest that watershed development policies have positively contributed to socio-economic transformation and livelihood enhancement of farmers in Marathwada, although challenges related to equitable access, sustainability, and institutional support remain.

Keywords: Watershed Development, Irrigation, Livelihood and Farmers' Perception.

Introduction:

Agriculture in India remains highly dependent on monsoon rainfall, especially in semi-arid and drought-prone regions. The Marathwada region of Maharashtra has historically faced acute water scarcity, frequent droughts, declining groundwater levels, crop failures, and seasonal migration. These challenges have adversely affected agricultural productivity and farmers' livelihoods. In response, watershed development has been adopted as an integrated approach to manage land and water resources in a sustainable manner. Watershed development policies in India aim at conserving soil and water, improving groundwater recharge, enhancing agricultural productivity, reducing vulnerability to climate variability, and strengthening rural livelihoods. By treating a hydrological unit rather

than administrative boundaries, watershed programmes emphasize participatory planning, community involvement, and holistic natural resource management. In Marathwada, several government-led and NGO-supported watershed programmes have been implemented to address chronic drought and agrarian distress. The present study attempts to assess the impact of watershed development policies on farmers in the Marathwada region, particularly focusing on socio-economic, environmental, and livelihood dimensions.

Methodology:

The study is based on **primary data** collected through a structured interview schedule. A total of **150 farmers** were selected from watershed-developed villages in Beed district

using purposive sampling. The field survey was conducted during **2021–22 and 2022–23**. Data were analyzed using simple statistical tools such as frequencies, percentages, and ranking methods. Comparative analysis was employed to assess changes before and after watershed development.

Objectives of the Study:

The objectives of the study are as follows as

1. To analyze the landholding status and irrigation conditions of farmers before and after watershed development.
2. To examine the impact of watershed development on farmers' income sources, crop productivity, and livelihood security.
3. To assess the social and environmental impacts of watershed development.

Result and Discussion:

Watershed development has a range of positive impacts on the community when implemented effectively. It leads to sustainable rural development through conserved natural resources, rises in agricultural productivity, increased employment generation and household income, and empowerment of residents in the watershed (Kerr, 2002; Palanisamia & Kumar, 2009). It is also a vehicle to enhance livelihood security of rural households in the watershed because it improves the livelihood asset base. Here are the primary benefits of watershed development: Conservation, up-gradation and utilization of natural endowments (land, water, vegetation, humans) Integrated, low-cost and simple to adopt technology. Reduce inequalities between rain-fed and irrigated areas.

Watershed Development and Crop Productivity:

Watershed management is an attempt to halt land degradation and a holistic process for

getting maximum production out of land. Watershed management implies rational utilisation of land and water resources for optimum and sustained production, with the minimum of hazard to natural resources.

Table -1 Crop productivity increased due to watershed area

Crop productivity increased?	No. of farmers	Percentage
Yes	142	94.67
No	8	5.33
Total	150	100.00

(Source: Field Survey - 2021-22)

It was shown in table-1 to know relationship between watershed development and productivity of crop. Out of 150 farmers 142 (94.67%) of farmers opinions where yes watershed development is main reason of increase in productivity of crop and 8 (5.33%) of farmers opinions watershed development is not main reason of increase in productivity of crop. It was concluded that majority of farmer's opinions that watershed development can increase in productivity of crop.

Figure-1 Crop productivity increased due to watershed area

Changes in Income Sources Farmers:

Watershed management is an attempt to halt land degradation and a holistic process for getting maximum production out of land. Watershed management implies rational utilisation of land and water resources for optimum and sustained production, with the minimum of hazard to natural resources. Conserve and utilize natural resources for higher

productivity of crops and more income/employment generation in addition to creating better climatic conditions. Various development programs including watershed development programmes. Watershed

development refers to the conservation; regeneration and the judicious use of all the natural resources particularly land, water, vegetation and animals and human development within the watershed.

Table -2 Watershed Impact on Farmers Income Sources

Sources	Before		After		Increases/dec reases
	No of farmers	Percentage	No of farmers	Percentage	
Agriculture	150	100.00	150	100	0.00
Livestock	12	8.00	19	12.67	4.67
Labour work	27	18.00	23	15.33	-2.67
Agro business	3	2.00	17	11.33	9.33
Agro trading	5	3.33	5	3.33	0.00

Note – Increases or decreases compare with n value. (n= 150)

(Source: Field Survey - 2021-22)

It was found that in a before watershed development, 100% of the farmers' source of income had agricultural, while it was remain constant after watershed development; before watershed development 8.00% of the farmers income source had livestock, while after it is 12.67% of farmers, it was increased by 4.67%; 18.00% of the Farmers' source of income was labour work, while after watershed development it decreased upto 15.33%.; before watershed development only 2.00% of the Farmers' do agro business, while watershed development it increased to 11.33% and there is no change in agro trading before or after watershed development. It was concluded that the farmer's source of income tends to change before or after watershed development. It was found that in the after-watershed development farmer's shift from traditional agricultural practices to indulge in small business activities or other farm side business activities which would fetch earning for them for their subsistence.

Figure-2 Watershed Impacts on Farmers Income Sources

Watershed development impact on sources of irrigation:

Watershed is thus the land and water area, which contributes runoff to a common point. A watershed is an area of land and water bounded by a drainage divide within which the surface runoff collects and flows out of the watershed through a single outlet into a larger river or lake. Hydrological, or direct, effects of doing this include reduction in downstream river flow, increased evaporation in the irrigated area, increased level in the water table as groundwater recharge in the area is increased and flow increased in the irrigated area.

Table-3 Watershed impact on sources of irrigation

Sr. No.	Source of irrigation	Number of Farmers					
		Before			After		
		Sufficient	Insufficient	Total	Sufficient	Insufficient	Total
1	Dug well	21 14.00	129 86.00	150 100.00	82 54.67	68 45.33	150 100.00
2	Bore well	19 12.67	131 87.33	150 100.00	68 45.33	82 54.67	150 100.00
3	River	5 3.33	145 96.67	150 100.00	12 8.00	138 92.00	150 100.00
4	Lake/Pond	3 2.00	147 98.00	150 100.00	19 12.67	131 87.33	150 100.00
5	Canal	21 14.00	129 86.00	150 100.00	21 14.00	129 86.00	150 100.00

Source: Field Survey - 2021-22

It was noticed from table that, in a before watershed development, 14.00% of the farmers had dug wells for irrigation while 86.00% of the farmers had dug well insufficient. In comparison, in a after watershed development 54.67% of farmers said that wells were sufficient for irrigation while 45.33% of farmers said that wells were insufficient; In a before watershed development 26.67% of the farmers had sufficient source of bore well and 87.33% of the farmers had insufficient source of bore well. In comparison, after watershed, bore well was sufficient for 45.33% of the farmers and bore well was insufficient for 54.67% of the farmers; before watershed development, 3.33% of the farmers had sufficient source of river for irrigation while after watershed development it increased upto 8.00%; before watershed development, 2.00% of the

farmers had sufficient source of pond for irrigation while after watershed development it increased upto 12.67%; it was noted that no changes sources of canal before or after watershed development. It was found that due to watershed development, sufficient water for agriculture is available from irrigation sources. However, the water level of wells, bore wells, lakes has increased and the area under irrigation has also increased.

Figure -3 Source of irrigation in normal and after watershed development

Table-4 Migration Trend for Employment

Migration for employment	Before		After	
	Number of Farmers	Percentage	Number of Farmers	Percentage
No	138	92.00	142	94.66
Yes	12	8.00	8	5.33
Total	150	100.00	150	100.00

Source: Field Survey - 2021-22

Table-4 shows the change in the migration status of farmers that before watershed development, 8.00% of farmers migrated from villages during summer, after watershed

development, summer migration shows that 2.66% of farmers migrated during summer. The catchment area has been reduced due to development.

Figure -4 Migrations for Employment

Figure -6 Types of watershed beneficiaries

Types of Watershed Beneficiaries:

Watershed development programme is peoples centered programme and people's participation in the programme has been made mandatory. The people have to form a watershed association and watershed committee for each watershed project. Watershed association, comprising all adults residing within a watershed project area. The committee is responsible for planning and development of watershed project for its area while developing the plan for the area, the committee has to take technical assistance from project implementation agency. Besides, the beneficiaries of the programme have to give voluntary donations / provide contribution in terms of labour, raw material, cash etc. for development activities and for operation and maintenance of assets created.

Table-6 Types of watershed beneficiaries

Type	Number of Farmers	Percentage
Direct	63	42.00
Indirect	87	58.00

Source: Field Survey - 2021-22

It was found from table 4.17 that 58.00 per cent of farmers directly beneficiaries of watershed, while 42.00 per cent of farmers indirect beneficiaries of watershed,

Conclusion:

The study clearly demonstrates that watershed development policies have had a positive and multidimensional impact on farmers in the Marathwada region. Improvements in irrigation coverage, groundwater recharge, crop productivity, income diversification, drinking water availability, environmental quality, and livelihood security are evident. Reduced migration and improved social conditions further highlight the transformative potential of watershed development. However, for long-term sustainability, continued maintenance of watershed structures, equitable water distribution, community participation, and institutional support are essential. Strengthening policy implementation and integrating watershed development with broader rural development strategies can further enhance its impact. The watershed development emerges as an effective policy instrument for addressing agrarian distress and promoting sustainable rural development in drought-prone regions.

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